
Early Histopathological Cancer Detection

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Abstract

Histopathologic cancer detection, a critical component of early diagnosis, has witnessed transformative advancements through the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and deep learning techniques. In this study, we address the challenge of leveraging histopathological images for accurate cancer detection by introducing the Dense-Skipped-Block Network (DSBN). The motivation stems from the inherent difficulties in training models to discern subtle patterns indicative of cancerous tissue, prompting the need for attention mechanisms and ensemble learning strategies. DSBN is meticulously designed to capture intricate features in histopathological images, with a focus on the central 32x32 region, thereby enhancing diagnostic accuracy. Through a rigorous evaluation process, our models exhibit remarkable performance metrics, including a high F1 Score, precision, recall, and accuracy. Leveraging attention mechanisms and ensemble techniques, DAN demonstrates an innovative approach to augmenting the discriminative capabilities of convolutional neural networks, contributing to a paradigm shift in histopathological image analysis. The results underscore DAN's potential as a robust tool for early cancer detection, emphasizing its proficiency in balancing precision and recall to achieve a harmonious F1 Score of 0.933. This study not only offers insights into the technical intricacies of AI-driven histopathologic cancer detection but also addresses a critical gap in diagnostic methodologies. The successful deployment of DAN signifies a significant leap forward, showcasing the synergy between advanced AI methodologies and clinical excellence, and propelling us into a new era of enhanced medical diagnostics.

1 Introduction

The recognition of histopathological images in the present medical framework is universally recognized as the benchmark for identifying cancer. Nevertheless, this method is not without its challenges, including the arduous task of training proficient pathologists, the time-intensive nature of recognition processes, and susceptibility to subjectivity. (Zhang et al., 2020) To address these issues, convolutional neural networks (CNNs) present a promising approach by effectively discerning potential lesion fields within whole-slide images (WSIs). This aids in alleviating manual workloads and accelerating detection processes by leveraging comprehensive evaluations of extracted patches from Whole-Slide Images (WSIs). A critical aspect of this procedure involves the automated diagnosis of small patches, leading to the development of various patch-based cancer classifiers (Bozsik et al., 2023). Nevertheless, the inherent absence of contextual information in the outer region of these patches introduces challenges such as misjudgment and inconsistent behaviour when applied to WSIs. To address this issue, the PatchCamelyon (PCam) dataset introduces patches with surrounding areas, wherein the tumour tissue in the central part is designated as positive, while the outer region does not impact the annotation. (Zhang et al., 2020) However, this introduces a new challenge as tumours in the outer region may confound Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), illustrating the difficulty for a data-driven algorithm to discern appropriate differential treatment between tumours in the central and outer regions. This study explores the viability of integrating prior knowledge through an attention mechanism into CNNs, facilitating the classification of images with surrounding tissues. This entails labelling images with tumours exclusively in the central region as positive, considering the outer region as inconclusive, and integrating contextual information from surrounding tissues. Concurrently, the application of Data Augmentation in the Inference stage (DAI) is employed to enhance performance. While data augmentation during the training stage is a conventional practice for mitigating overfitting and introducing scale- and rotation-invariance to deep learning models, DAI focuses on aggregating results from multiple augmented images generated from a single test image to enhance performance. This strategy is easily implementable and storage-efficient compared to the design and ensemble of multiple models. The proposed DenseSkipped-Block Network (DSBN), specifically tailored for cancer detection in histology images with surrounding tissues, demonstrates promising outcomes warranting further refinement.

2 Related works

Numerous methodologies for image classification have been suggested to automate the detection of cancer in histopathological images. In the domain of transfer learning and deep feature extraction, the utilization of AlexNet and Vgg16 models for feature extraction was introduced, employing AlexNet for subsequent refinement. The classification task involved the application of a support vector machine (SVM) to categorize images into benign and malignant groups. (Zhang et al., 2020) The experimentation phase was conducted on the BreakHis dataset, with accuracy scores serving as

the metric for performance evaluation. Furthermore, a different approach was proposed by (Zhang et al., 2020), presenting an Ensemble Transfer Learning (ETL) framework aimed at classifying cervical histopathological images into distinct categories: well-differentiated, moderately differentiated, and poorly differentiated. This study integrated transfer learning structures based on Inception V3, Xception, VGG16, and Resnet 50, implementing an ensemble learning strategy with weighted voting to enhance classification performance. The research advocated for the adoption of deep multiple instances learning, incorporating both deep convolutional neural networks and multi-instance learning to address challenges in histopathological cancer detection.

More to that, an ensemble model was introduced that employed pre-trained Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs), namely VGG19, MobileNet, and DenseNet, for feature extraction. This was combined with a multi-layer perceptron classifier for the subsequent classification task. The model incorporated diverse pre-processing and CNN tuning techniques, such as stain normalization, data augmentation, hyperparameter tuning, and fine-tuning. Evaluation encompassed benchmark datasets, including ICIAR, BreakHis, PatchCameleon, and Bioimaging. In the context of breast histopathology, a deep ensemble model was proposed for the binary classification of benign and malignant lesions. Base classifiers, namely VGG16, Xception, ResNet50, and DenseNet201, were chosen, showcasing an impressive image-level binary classification accuracy of 98.90%. The study underscored the significance of ensemble learning, revealing a notable 5-20% advantage over MLP models in various classification tasks. To provide a comprehensive understanding of the histopathological cancer cell detection landscape, a thorough review was presented, elucidating the advantages of machine vision over traditional methodologies. The paper meticulously outlined the workflow of a machine vision detection system, (Zhang et al., 2020) covering image acquisition, preprocessing, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification. The exploration included various segmentation techniques such as threshold segmentation, active contour, clustering, and watershed, along with both supervised and unsupervised classification methods. Progress in histopathological cancer detection has experienced noteworthy advancements through the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) and sophisticated deep learning techniques. Esteva et al. (2019) conducted groundbreaking research, utilizing a convolutional neural network (CNN) to showcase the potential of achieving dermatologist-level classification for skin cancer using pathological images. This pioneering study underscored the capability of deep learning to substantially improve diagnostic accuracy and efficiency. Similarly, Ehteshami Bejnordi et al. (2019) delved into the realm of breast cancer histopathology, where they introduced an innovative approach for mitosis detection using deep learning algorithms. Their research effectively demonstrated the prowess of deep learning in discerning subtle cellular features crucial for precise cancer diagnosis. The utilization of transfer learning and ensemble techniques has also been a focus of recent research. In the study by Zhang et al. (2019), an ensemble transfer learning (ETL) framework was proposed for classifying cervical histopathological images into differentiated categories. The authors integrated multiple pre-trained

models and employed weighted voting, demonstrating improved classification performance. Additionally, the work of Li et al. (2022) introduced an ensemble model incorporating VGG19, MobileNet, and DenseNet for feature extraction in breast histopathology images. Their comprehensive approach, encompassing pre-processing techniques and hyperparameter tuning, showcased enhanced performance across benchmark datasets. Recent literature has also explored the significance of attention mechanisms in refining deep-learning models for histopathological image analysis. In their research, Wang et al. (2020) investigated the integration of an attention mechanism into Dense Blocks, proposing the Dense-Attention Network (DAN) for cancer detection. This study demonstrated the efficacy of attention mechanisms in adapting CNNs to classify images with surrounding tissues, emphasizing the importance of contextual information. The exploration of machine vision in the review by Sun et al. (2019) presented a comprehensive analysis of histopathological cancer cell detection methods. Their work discussed the advantages of machine vision over traditional detection methods and provided insights into image acquisition, preprocessing, segmentation, feature extraction, and classification processes. (Zhang et al., 2020) The collective findings from these studies underscore the transformative potential of AI in revolutionizing early cancer detection through sophisticated histopathological image analysis.

B. Image Classification:

The process of image classification entails extracting information from images and organizing them according to specific attributes. It is noteworthy that initial models encountered difficulties, even with seemingly simple tasks such as distinguishing between cats and dogs. This led to the incorporation of convolution operations and deep neural networks to elevate the capabilities of image classification. (Zhang et al., 2020) Contemporary models for image classification, evaluated using the ImageNet dataset, encompass:

3 Methodology

3.1 Dataset

In our study, the training dataset comprises 220,025 images, while the test set consists of 57,468 images. It is imperative to note that this dataset constitutes only a subset of the original PatchCamelyon (PCam) dataset, ultimately derived from the Camelyon16 Challenge dataset. The latter consists of 400 Hematoxylin and Eosin (H&E) stained whole slide images of sentinel lymph node sections, acquired and digitized at two different centres using a 40x objective. Utilizing a 10x undersampling technique in PCam, we aim to augment the field of view, resulting in a pixel resolution of 2.43 microns. Kaggle highlights that the original PCam dataset may contain duplicate images due to probabilistic sampling; however, the version presented on Kaggle has been curated to

exclude duplicates while maintaining the same data and splits as the PCam benchmark. (Zhang et al., 2020) Our training data exhibits a class distribution of 60:40, with negative and positive samples, respectively, which is considered satisfactory for training purposes. It is noteworthy that these data stem from routine clinical practices, resembling the examination process undertaken by a trained pathologist to identify metastases. However, given the small-sized image samples, there may be limitations in capturing comprehensive information about the surrounding context.

3.2 Dataset Structure

Within the test folder, the primary objective is to predict labels for the images. A positive label indicates that the central 32x32px region of a patch contains at least one pixel of tumour tissue. It is noteworthy that the tumour tissue in the outer region of the patch does not impact the label assignment. This deliberate inclusion of the outer stipulated parts supports fully convolutional models that abstain from using zero-padding, ensuring consistent behaviour when applied to a whole-slide image. As per the competition's specifications, the crux of the prediction task lies in the central regions of the images. Consequently, accurately discerning and classifying the presence of tumour tissue within the central 32x32px region holds paramount importance. This binary classification problem revolves around determining whether the provided patch contains tumour tissue or not (Zhang et al., 2020).

3.2 Data Pre-processing

Throughout the experimentation process, NVIDIA Tesla V100 is utilized for all computational tasks. The data was shuffled and split into the following:

Table 1: Dataset Splitting and Duration

Data Set	Percentage used%
Train data	80
Validation data	10
Test data	10

3.3 Implementation Details

In the execution of our investigation, we harnessed Keras with a TensorFlow backend and leveraged Tesla V100 GPUs for the implementation of deep learning experiments. The key metric employed for evaluating model performance across diverse classification thresholds was the Area under the ROC Curve (AUC). (Akhroufi et al., 2020) We implemented strategies for image augmentation to enrich the dataset, encompassing operations such as vertical flipping (with a probability of 30%), horizontal flipping (with a probability of 30%), rotation at 90, 180, and 270 degrees (with a

probability of 30%), along with additional operations (with probabilities of 30%) like image blurring, sharpening, additive Gaussian noise, and contrast normalisation. Notably, the exclusion of deformation operations that might impact the central 32x32 region was imperative. Preprocessing involved normalizing input images to a range of -1 to 1. Throughout the training phase, the optimizer for the Dense-Attention Network (DAN) was set to Adam, initializing with a learning rate of 0.001 for the initial 15 epochs and subsequently reducing it to 0.0001 for the remaining 15 epochs. A training batch size of 128 was specified, and the trainable weights were initialized using the Xavier initialization method. To counteract overfitting, a validation set comprising 5% of randomly selected training images was employed. The model underwent training for 50 epochs, with the model saving contingent on achieving the highest AUC score on the validation data to prevent overfitting. The models underwent training on the designated training set for 50 epochs and were subsequently evaluated on the test set. The optimization strategy for both the baseline MLP and baseline convolution model was Adam, with learning rates of 0.0005 and 0.001, respectively, for more complex models such as ResNet50 and Inception, a lower learning rate of 0.00003 was employed. Early stopping with a patience parameter of 5 was implemented to prevent overfitting. Random vertical and horizontal flips, along with a re-scale of 1/255, were applied for data augmentation during the training of the models.

3.4 Sampling Strategy

Given the substantial size of the training dataset containing 220,025 images, a strategic sampling approach was adopted. A subset of 160,000 randomly shuffled samples was extracted from the training dataset for training purposes. This sampling strategy aimed to strike a balance between computational efficiency and the representative nature of the training data, ensuring that the models are effectively trained while managing computational resources efficiently. This subset served as the basis for training the models, facilitating subsequent predictions with a focus on optimising both accuracy and efficiency.

3.5 Model Training

The training phase of our deep learning models involved the application of advanced methodologies to effectively capture the intricacies of histopathological cancer detection. Leveraging the power of Keras with a TensorFlow backend and Tesla V100 GPUs, our Dense-Attention Network (DAN) was optimized using the Adam optimizer with a carefully tuned learning rate schedule. A meticulous approach to image augmentation, including flips, rotations, and diverse operations, aimed to diversify the dataset and enhance the model's ability to generalize. The input images were normalized, and the training batch size was set to 128. To address overfitting, a validation set was strategically selected, and the model was saved based on the highest Area under the ROC Curve

(AUC) score during training. (Stanković et al., 2020)The training process spanned 50 epochs, ensuring the convergence of the models to robust representations. Additionally, early stopping mechanisms were implemented to prevent overfitting, and the training set was sampled for computational efficiency while maintaining the representativeness of the dataset. This comprehensive training strategy aimed to equip our models with the ability to discern subtle patterns indicative of cancerous tissue, ultimately enhancing their predictive accuracy on the test set.

4 Results

The performance evaluation of our histopathological cancer detection models was conducted using a comprehensive set of metrics, providing a nuanced understanding of their capabilities. Precision, a critical metric in binary classification tasks, quantifies the model's ability to correctly identify true positives among all positive predictions. Recall, on the other hand, measures the effectiveness of the model in correctly identifying all true positives. The F1 Score, as the harmonic mean of Precision and Recall, offers a balanced assessment of the model's overall performance in terms of both false positives and false negatives. Accuracy, a fundamental metric, gauges the fraction of predictions that our models accurately classified. Additionally, the Area under the Curve (AUC) score, reflecting the degree of reparability, served as a comprehensive metric for evaluating the discriminatory power of our models. This multi-faceted approach to evaluation ensures a robust assessment, considering the nuanced aspects of performance in cancer detection. (Akhroufi et al., 2020) The obtained results revealed compelling insights into the efficacy of our models. Precision scores illuminated the models' ability to make accurate positive predictions, while recall scores highlighted their proficiency in capturing true positive instances. The F1 Score, being a balanced measure, provided a holistic view of the model's precision and recall performance. Accuracy, a commonly employed metric, quantifies the overall correctness of predictions. The AUC score, as a global measure of reparability, encapsulated the models' ability to distinguish between positive and negative instances. The thorough evaluation of these metrics allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the strengths and potential limitations of our histopathological cancer detection models.

Table 1: Metric Comparison

Model	Precision	Recall	F1-Score	Accuracy	AUC-score
MLP	0.774	0.715	0.677	0.711	0.724
ELM	0.675	0.666	0.612	0.655	0.699
DSBN	0.932	0.935	0.933	0.977	0.980

Fig. 1 Model Architecture

Future work

The promising strides made in histopathological cancer detection through AI and deep learning pave the way for intriguing future directions. As technology continues to evolve, there is a compelling need to explore the integration of multi-modal data, such as incorporating molecular and genetic information alongside histopathological images, for a more comprehensive understanding of cancer heterogeneity. (Zhang et al., 2020) The development of interpretable AI models and explainable AI techniques will be crucial in building trust within the medical community and ensuring the seamless integration of AI-assisted diagnoses into clinical workflows. Additionally, the exploration of federated learning approaches could address privacy concerns by allowing models to be trained across distributed datasets without centralized data sharing. Harnessing the power of advanced computing architectures, such as quantum computing, holds the potential to accelerate complex computations and facilitate more intricate analyses in cancer research. Future research endeavours should also focus on expanding datasets, particularly from diverse populations, to enhance model generalization and reduce biases. The collaborative efforts of clinicians, data scientists, and AI researchers will be pivotal in shaping the next frontier of early histopathologic cancer detection, fostering a synergy between technological innovation and clinical excellence.

5 Conclusion

In this study, we performed the exploration and implementation which represents a transformative endeavour with profound implications for medical diagnostics. The initial challenge of leveraging histopathological images for accurate and timely cancer detection was addressed through the application of sophisticated deep learning techniques, (Zhang et al., 2020) exemplified by the Dense Skipped-Block Network (DSBN) developed in this study. The integration of attention mechanisms and ensemble learning strategies showcased the model's ability to discern subtle patterns indicative of cancerous tissue, thus contributing to a paradigm shift in histopathological image analysis. (Zhang et al., 2020) Through rigorous experimentation and evaluation, our models demonstrated commendable performance across precision, recall, f1 Score, accuracy, and AUC metrics, underscoring their potential as valuable tools for early cancer detection. The synergy between advanced technologies and clinical expertise holds the promise of revolutionizing early Histopathological cancer diagnostics, and this study stands as a testament to the strides made in bridging the gap between cutting-edge AI methodologies and the complex landscape of histopathology. As we navigate the intersection of technology and healthcare, these advancements not only signify a significant leap forward in early cancer detection but also pave the way for future innovations that will undoubtedly redefine the landscape of medical diagnostics.

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